

Trichohyalin (TCHH) : Machine learning discoveries of 2nd order synergy in Meningiomas

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Abstract

Background : Trichohyalin, encoded by TCHH, associates in regular arrays with keratin intermediate filaments (KIF) of the inner root sheath cells of the hair follicle and the granular layer of the epidermis. It is a known substrate of transglutaminases. TCHH has been implicated in alopecia areata, uncombable hair syndrome, liver metastasis in colorectal cancer and hair matrix keratinocyte proliferation and hair follicles (HF) pigmentation. However, its role in meningiomas has not yet been determined completely. Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 tumors from all 3 World Health Organization (WHO) grades (I through III) using clinical, gene expression, and sequencing data and using unsupervised clustering analysis identified 3 molecular types (A, B, and C) that reliably predicted recurrence. Further, these groups did not directly correlate with the WHO grading system, which classifies more than half of the tumors in the most aggressive molecular type as benign. **Issue** : Increasing evidence point to the fact that meningioma classification and grading, that is based on histopathology does not always accurately predict tumor aggressiveness and recurrence behaviour and knowledge of the underlying biology of the treatment resistant meningiomas and the impact of genetic alterations in these tumors, is lacking. At the current stage more genomic studies are required to unravel the role of other genes and their interactions with other genetic factors. **Resolution** : In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. Adapting this search engine to the Meningioma dataset, i present here 2nd order combinations of TCHH, some of which have been known to exist via wet lab experiments, but many are yet to be tested. The reveals combinations might help oncologists/biologists test possible hypotheses that might be the causing factors in meningioma. Further, in my limited grasp, if proven true, the combinations revealed by the search engine might pave way for development of gene based therapies aimed at resolving pathological issues related to meningiomas.

[☆]ML dicoveries of TCHH synergy in Meningiomas

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1. Introduction

1.1. Meningioma

Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. They arise from the arachnoid cap cells. These arachnoid cap cells are specialized cells that make up the arachnoid mater (one of the three protective membranes covering the brain and spinal cord). The arachnoid mater is one of the three meninges. The other two that constitute the meninges are dura mater and pia mater.

1.1.1. World Health Organization (WHO) classification

The meningiomas are classified into three grades by WHO under the Central Nervous System tumours, namely, Grade I (benign), Grade II (atypical) and Grade III (anaplastic/malignant), based on histopathology or subtype (Louis et al. [3]). As of 2021, there exists 12 histopathological meningioma subtypes according to a mini-review by Torp et al. [4]. They are meningothelial, fibrous, transitional, psammomatous, angiomatous, microcystic, secretory, lymphoplasmacyte-rich, atypical, chordoid, clear cell and anaplastic (malignant) meningioma.

1.1.2. Historical perspective

Czarnetzki et al. [5] investigated a skull that was excavated at Steinheim/Murr (Baden-Württemberg, Germany) and consisted of a well preserved plagioccephalic cranium, with most of the facial skeleton intact. Their results of stratigraphical dating suggested the fossil specimen of *Homo steinheimensis*, was about 3,65,000 years old. In the fossile, they found that several features of the inner cranial table were consistent with a diagnosis of meningioma.

As documented in Okonkwo and Laws Jr [6], in 1614, Felix Plater, Professor of Medicine, issued a case report from the University of Basel on Caspar Bonecurtius, a noble knight stating -

began to lose his mind gradually over a two year period, to such an extent that finally he was completely stupefied and did nothing rationally. He had no desire for food and ate only when forcibly fed. ... Finally after matters had gone on thus for six months, he died.

Further, the autopsy report of Plater stated the following -

a round fleshy tumor, like an acorn. It was hard and full of holes and was as large as a medium-sized apple. It was covered with its own membrane and was entwined with veins. However, it was free of all connections with the matter of the brain, so much so that when it was removed by hand, it left behind a remarkable cavity.

This was the first case in the history that documented a patient with a lesion that was most compatible with a meningioma.

Next, in a contribution by Italian scientists, Paterniti [7] documents the first contribution of Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri in 1813 in a manuscript *Trattato di Chirurgia Pratica*, which was never published. Its discovery was made accidentally by David Giordano, who referred in detail in an article on surgeon of Pisa in *La chirurgia di Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri*. *Riv Storia Sci MedNat*. 1927: XVIII (3-4): 75-106. The unpublished manuscript of 488 pages describes that Vacca Berlinhieri proposed and performed a most bold radical operation. After a craniectomy with five or six burr holes on the outskirts of the fungus, the tumor was removed together the dura mater from which it originated, tying the cut vessels.

In 1847, Zanobi Pecchioli, Professor of Clinical Surgery and Operative Medicine at Modena and then at Siena University, published an account of surgeries performed during 16 years, from 1832 to 1847 (16 of the 1524 reported operations involved trephining of the skull). In one of these interventions, he carried out on July 29 1835, in Siena, for the resection of a meningioma, a defined fungus of the duramater. The case was not referred in the literature by Pecchioli but was described by in Pecchioli [8]. Finally, Cushing [9] coined the modern term of "meningioma".

1.1.3. Pathophysiology

Meningiomas arise from arachnoidal cap cells, most of which are near the vicinity of the venous sinuses, and this is the site of greatest prevalence for meningioma formation.

Figure 1: A schematic diagram of different pathways in different meningiomas, as provided by Szulzewsky et al. [12] under CC-BY Attribution 4.0 International license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

The dural venous sinuses (also called dural/cerebral/cranial sinuses) are venous sinuses (channels) found between the periosteal and meningeal layers of dura mater in the brain. They receive blood from the cerebral veins, and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) from the subarachnoid space via arachnoid granulations. They mainly empty into the internal jugular vein. Cranial venous sinuses communicate with veins outside the skull through emissary veins. These communications help to keep the pressure of blood in the sinuses constant. (contributors [10] and Pamir et al. [11]) A schematic diagram for different pathways in different meningiomas has been provided in figure 1.

1.2. Trichohyalin (TCHH)

In 1903, Voerner [13] documented a study on trichohyalin while studying the anatomy of hair and of the hair root.

Rothnagel and Rogers [14] isolated and characterized a precursor protein associated with the formation of the citrulline-containing intermediate filaments of the hair follicle. They isolated the protein (molecular weight of 190,000) from sheep wool follicles. Using tissue immunochemical methods, they localized the Mr 190,000 protein to the trichohyalin granules of the developing inner root sheath of the wool follicle. Based on this, they proposed that the old term trichohyalin be retained to describe this Mr 190,000 protein.

Fietz et al. [15] isolated a partial cDNA clone for sheep trichohyalin.

In the studies of desmosomes, O'Keefe et al. [16] found trichohyalin, in a citric

acid-insoluble fraction ("desmosome preparation") from tongue epithelium. Their immunofluorescence studies showed that it is a major protein of the filiform papillae of the tongue of mammals. Further, it is present in isolated cells of the stratum granulosum of some regions of epidermis in a subset of cells containing filaggrin and in the nail matrix. Immunoblotting confirmed that trichohyalin was present in both, tongue and epidermis.

Lee et al. [17] determined the full-length sequence of human trichohyalin. They showed that trichohyalin might have at least 3 important functions in cells, namely -

- human trichohyalin was predicted to be an elongated flexible rod (at least 215 nm long) and function as a KIF-associated protein by cross-linking the filaments in loose networks;
- trichohyalin was found to be similar to, but several times longer than, involucrin, a known cell envelope constituent. Together, involucrin and trichohyalin might serve as scaffold proteins in the organization of the cell envelope or even anchor the cell envelope to the KIF network; and
- trichohyalin possessed a pair of functional Ca-binding domains of the EF-hand type at its amino terminus that might be involved in its Ca-dependent postsynthetic processing during terminal differentiation.

TCHH is an insoluble α -helixrich protein that forms rigid structures as a result of postsynthetic modifications by two Ca^{2+} -dependent enzymes, namely -

- transglutaminases (TGases) (protein cross-linking) and
- peptidyl-arginine deiminase (conversion of arginines to citrullines with loss of organized structure).

Tarcsa et al. [18] explored in vitro, the order of processing of TCHH to fulfill these functions, using an expressed truncated, more soluble form TCHH-8.

1.3. Roles of TCHH in different disease

Alopecia areata (AA) is a common putative autoimmune hair loss disorder. Leung et al. [19] isolated AA-reactive hair follicle (HF)-specific antigens from normal human scalp anagen HF extracts from 10 AA patients. Their double immunofluorescence studies using AA (and control sera) together with a monoclonal antibody to trichohyalin showed that AA sera contained immunoreactivity that colocalized with trichohyalin in the growth phase-specific inner root sheath of HF. In conclusion, their study supported the involvement of an immune response to anagen-specific HFs antigens in AA. It also specifically suggested that an immune response to trichohyalin and Keratin 16 (K16) might have a role in the pathogenesis of the enigmatic disorder.

Uncombable hair syndrome (UHS), also known as spun glass hair syndrome / pili trianguli et canaliculi or cheveux incoiffables is a rare anomaly of the hair shaft that occurs in children and improves with age. In a total of 11 children, Basmanav et al. [20] reported the identification of UHS-causative mutations located in the three genes, i.e peptidylarginine deiminase 3 (PADI3), transglutaminase 3 (TGM3), and TCHH. They observed that all the children carried homozygous or compound heterozygous mutations in one of these 3 genes, thus indicating an autosomal-recessive inheritance pattern in the majority of UHS case subjects. Further, they found that the two enzymes PADI3 and TGM3, and their target structural protein TCHH, were all involved in hair shaft formation.

Methylation of circulating free DNA (CfDNA) has emerged as an efficient marker of tumor screening and prognostics. Chen et al. [21] identified significantly increased

methylation of TCHH in the process of **liver metastasis (LM)** in **colorectal cancer (CRC)**. Their MethyLight analysis of TCHH methylation in CfDNA displayed a promisingly discriminative power between CRC with and without liver metastasis. Their results indicated the potential of TCHH methylation in CfDNA as a monitoring marker of LM in CRC.

Hair follicles (HFs) are immersed within dermal white adipose tissue (dWAT). Nicu et al. [22] investigated how perifollicular adipocytes affect the physiology of human anagen scalp HFs. Ex vivo, they found that dWAT tendentially promoted hair shaft production, and significantly stimulated **hair matrix keratinocyte proliferation** and **HF pigmentation**. Further, they observed that both dWAT pericytes and PREF1/DLK1⁺ adipocyte progenitors secreted HGF during human HFdWAT co-culture, for which the c-Met receptor was expressed in the hair matrix and dermal papilla. Their microarray analysis of the hair matrix revealed that dWAT-derived HGF upregulated keratin (K) genes (K-27/73/75/84/86) and TCHH. Mechanistically, they found that HGF stimulated Wnt/ β -catenin activity in the human hair matrix (increased AXIN2, LEF1) by upregulating WNT-6/10B, and inhibiting SFRP1 in the dermal papilla.

Many of the different synergies represented as combinations of genes/proteins have been experimentally tested and published. However, there are combinations that have yet to be explored. I address the problem of identifying these unexplored combinations via use of a machine learning based search engine in the next section.

1.4. Insight behind the work

Across all search engines has the fundamental principle remains the same i.e to capture the pattern available in the data and based on that pattern, rank a list of queries. Different algorithms can be applied, however if the fundamental pattern is captured accurately, then the rankings will remain approximately the same, with slight variations, across the different kinds of search engines used. I use one search engine, however, vary the way the patterns are captured via use of different sensitivity methods. Each sensitivity method uses a different flavour/mathematical formulation to compute the sensitivity indices to estimate the influence of the involved factors. These involved factors are genes that play a role in cell biology, in the above research. The insight is that all methods will capture the sensitivity of the involved factors based on their recorded regulations and the search engine will rank the combination of factors based on these sensitivity indices. Since the role of involved factors are captured properly, the search engine will give appropriate rankings to the combinations, thus capturing which gene combinations might be playing significantly in a biological phenomena. The above work shows rankings for experimentally confirmed combinations as well as unexplored/untested combinations. These rankings are not just numbers. They point to the existence of biological synergy in the form of gene combinations, whether tested in wet lab or unexplored till now. Finally, the findings suggest that the rankings are conserved across the different sensitivity methods used.

1.5. Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. The work uses SVM package by Joachims [23] in https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html. I use the adaptation to rank 2^{nd} order gene combinations. The sensitivity package by Pujol et al. [24] was used to develop the search engine pipeline. The current research uses the Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion (HSIC) and SOBOL method, implemented in the sensitivity package mentioned above. I use three different kernels under the HSIC method namely, • laplace, • linear and • rbf. For SOBOL method, I use • sobol-2002, and • sobol-jansen. Each of these variants or kernels have been implemented in the sensitivity package and option has been provided in the search engine code to generate the rankings for a particular gene, using a choice of a kernel/variant at a time. Technical details about the variants and kernels can be found in references citetd in Pujol et al. [24].

2. Methods

2.1. Static data from Patel et al. [1]

Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 meningioma samples from 140 patients, and according to the WHO histopathological classification system for meningioma, they found 121 tumors were of grade I (benign), 32 were of grade II (atypical), and 7 were of grade III (malignant). To determine whether meningiomas could be differentiated based on gene expression profiles, they used principal component analysis (PCA) on a discovery set of 97 tumors (i.e 77 WHO grade I and 20 WHO grade II). Next, they employed nonnegative matrix factorization (NMF) clustering (a unsupervised machine-learning approach) for $k = 2$ to $k = 7$ using the 1,500 genes that varied most among the tumor samples. They report that after 1,000 iterations, 3 clusters ($k = 3$) emerged as providing the best fit as determined by the consensus membership, cophenetic, and silhouette scores. They evaluated the cluster significance of the 3 subtypes using SigClust (Huang et al. [25]) and observed statistical significance between cluster boundaries, which exhibited significant differences in WHO grade representation.

2.2. Design for static data from Patel et al. [1]

The procedure begins with the listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes. Here n can be the choice of the biologist. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represent a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. Since the sensitivity analysis methods require a sample for a particular observation, a steep gaussian distribution was generated with a jitter (noise) added to the deviation from the reported point measurement of 0.005. In this experiment, the distribution contained 10 measurements (including the point of measurement under consideration). This is repeated for each point of measurement.

To have an averaged ranking, the experiment was designed to run for 25 iterations. In each iteration, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as

per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in a required format. Details of formatting the data have not been presented in the article to maintain the fluidity and brevity. Interested readers can find examples of formatting the data in the sensitivity analysis package in R. Sensitivity analysis and its relevance in systems biology have been covered in a recently published article by Sinha [26], which forms the foundation for this work. After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, for a chosen sensitivity analysis method, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Here, the indices are averaged per combination to have a mean index value. These index values form the discriminative features for a particular combination. For a k^{th} order combination, a vector of k elements or indices forms a feature vector. Thus for C_k^n combinations there will be C_k^n vectors, each containing k elements. Next, SVM_{learn}^{Rank} Joachims [23] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM_{classify}^{Rank}$ Joachims [23]. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R Team [27], in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use source("extractMeningiomadata.R") • use source("manuscript-2-2.R") • use source("SVMRank-Results-S-mean.R").

2.3. Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R

The execution begins by some preprocessing of the file containing the information regarding the down regulated genes via `source("extractMeningiomadata.R")`. The library containing the sensitivity analysis methods is then loaded in the interface using the command `library(sensitivity)` (Note - this package can be downloaded for free from <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/sensitivity/index.html>). Next a gaussian distribution for a particular transcript level for a gene is generated to have a sample. This is needed in the computation of sensitivity index for that particular gene. A gene of particular choice is selected (in blue) and the choice of the combination is made (here $k = 2$). Later a kernel is used (here rbf for HSIC method). 25 different indices are generated which help in generating aggregate rank using these 25 indices. The Support vector ranking algorithm is employed to generate the scores for different combinations and these scores are then sorted out. This is done using the command `source("SVMRank - Results - S - mean.R")`. A file is generated that contains the combinations in increasing order of influence. Note that 1 means lowest rank and vice versa, for 2^{nd} order combinations for any gene using a particular density based

sensitivity index.

2.4. Regarding biological insight

For the recorded gene expression values, the sensitivity indices are computed. The search engine uses the kernel based density method. The kernel method takes the data, that is in a lower dimensional plane and projects it to a higher dimensional plane, with an idea that in a higher dimensional plane, there exists a dot product between the projected data. To simply state, the idea is that in a higher dimensional plane the nonlinearities between the data (in lower dimensional plane) will be captured and the data may be segregated from each other via a hyperplane. So, irrespective of the method used to measure the gene expression values, if the measurements capture biological information (to whatever extent they can), then the kernel method will be able to capture the nonlinearities/synergies, if existing and allow the sensitivity analysis method (here density based method) to estimate the strength of influence of each of the factors. Based on the sensitivity indices of combinations of a particular order, the search engine ranks the combinations. Details of search engine are provided in the published work in Sinha [2].

It is important to note that the search engine will not give insight about the mechanism of synergy between the components of a combination. However, if the synergy exists between components of an unexplored/untested combination, then the sensitivity indices will capture the influence of these components taken together (which form a combination of interest) and will rank the combination appropriately. These rankings provide insight about which combination a biologist/oncologist might want to test in a forest of combinations for a given scenario in a cell (whether normal or pathological).

3. Results & Discussion

3.1. TCHH related synergies

Note - TCHH was found to be upregulated in Type B. Upregulation was defined as Type logFC to be > 1 and $FDR \leq 0.001$, in Patel et al. [1]. Also, sorting of scores by the machine learning algorithm were done in ascending order, i.e - top is lowest in ranking. A total of 392 2^{nd} order combinations of TCHH were recorded.

3.1.1. TCHH - individual genes

The following genes in combination with TCHH showed high rankings - amyloid beta precursor protein binding family A member 2 (APBA2), collagen type IX alpha 2 chain (COL9A2), carboxypeptidase A1 (CPA1), procollagen C-endopeptidase enhancer (PCOLCE), endoglin (ENG), cadherin 6 (CDH6), par-3 family cell polarity regulator beta (PARD3B), Wnt ligand secretion mediator (WLS), PHD finger protein 24 (PHF24), plasminogen activator, urokinase (PLAU), basic helix-loop-helix family member e41 (BHLHE41), HIVEP zinc finger 3 (HIVEP3), phospholipase C beta 2 (PLCB2), fibulin 5 (FBLN5), chromosome 1 open reading frame 162 (C1orf162),

RNA binding motif single stranded interacting protein 3 (RBMS3), LanC like family member 3 (LANCL3), S100 calcium binding protein B (S100B), collagen type XXVI alpha 1 chain (COL26A1), sialic acid binding Ig like lectin 16 (gene/pseudogene) (SIGLEC16), matrix remodeling associated 8 (MXRA8), vascular cell adhesion molecule 1 (VCAM1), NLR family pyrin domain containing 3 (NLRP3), frizzled related protein (FRZB), C1q and TNF related 7 (C1QTNF7), amyloid beta precursor protein binding family B member 2 (APBB2), 15-hydroxyprostaglandin dehydrogenase (HPGD), coagulation factor II thrombin receptor like 2 (F2RL2), Rho related BTB domain containing 3 (RHOBTB3), EBF transcription factor 1 (EBF1), myozenin 3 (MYOZ3), somatomedin B and thrombospondin type 1 domain containing (SBSPON), carbonic anhydrase 3 (CA3), PDZ domain containing ring finger 4 (PDZRN4), transmembrane protein 130 (TMEM130), microfibril associated protein 4 (MFAP4), nicotinamide N-methyltransferase (NNMT), proline rich transmembrane protein 2 (PRRT2), cytochrome P450 family 2 subfamily S member 1 (CYP2S1), 5'-nucleotidase domain containing 2 (NT5DC2), RAB31, member RAS oncogene family (RAB31), energy homeostasis associated (ENHO), carnitine palmitoyltransferase 1C (CPT1C), coiled-coil domain containing 126 (CCDC126), serine/threonine kinase 32A (STK32A), G protein-coupled receptor 27 (GPR27), secretogranin II (SCG2), StAR related lipid transfer domain containing 5 (STARD5), homeobox B2 (HOXB2), purinergic receptor P2Y14 (P2RY14), calcium binding protein 4 (CABP4), solute carrier organic anion transporter family member 3A1 (SLCO3A1), BCL2 family apoptosis regulator BOK (BOK), myozenin 1 (MYOZ1), phosphodiesterase 4D interacting protein (PDE4DIP), serine rich and transmembrane domain containing 1 (SERTM1), NME/NM23 family member 9 (NME9), PLAG1 zinc finger (PLAG1), phospholipase C beta 1 (PLCB1), neurotrimin (NTM), regulator of G protein signaling 6 (RGS6), pappalysin 1 (PAPPA), olfactomedin like 1 (OLFML1), protein kinase D1 (PRKD1), colony stimulating factor 1 (CSF1), fibronectin leucine rich transmembrane protein 2 (FLRT2), protein kinase cGMP-dependent 1 (PRKG1), SHC adaptor protein 4 (SHC4), ankyrin repeat domain 20 family member A5, pseudogene (ANKRD20A5P), kelch repeat and BTB domain containing 12 (KBTBD12), low density lipoprotein receptor class A domain containing 2 (LDLRAD2), placenta associated 9 (PLAC9), nuclear GTPase, germinal center associated (NUGGC), family with sequence similarity 180 member A (FAM180A), membrane metalloendopeptidase (MME), family with sequence similarity 180 member B (FAM180B), DLG associated protein 2 (DLGAP2), matrix metallopeptidase 17 (MMP17), delta like canonical Notch ligand 1 (DLL1), zinc finger protein 521 (ZNF521), ryanodine receptor 3 (RYR3), ras homolog family member T1 pseudogene 2 (RHOT1P2), synaptotagmin 15 (SYT15), family with sequence similarity 155 member A (FAM155A), transmembrane protein 240 (TMEM240), vitrin (VIT), ankyrin repeat domain 20 family member A9, pseudogene (ANKRD20A9P), glutathione peroxidase 3 (GPX3), high mobility group box 3 pseudogene 7 (HMGB3P7), teneurin transmembrane protein 3 (TENM3), ITGB2 antisense RNA 1 (ITGB2-AS1), cytochrome P450 family 4 subfamily F member 29, pseudogene (CYP4F29P) and sorting nexin 18 pseudogene 13 (SNX18P13).

Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I tabulate the rankings of 2nd order combination of TCHH with the above list, that were reported to be upregulated in Patel et al. [1]. Table 1 and 2 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed

by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 3 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 1 and 2.

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS TCHH									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T TCHH									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
APBA2 - TCHH	227	275	232	40	COL9A2 - TCHH	266	274	198	352
CPA1 - TCHH	204	242	69	347	PCOLCE - TCHH	236	239	200	390
ENG - TCHH	217	230	182	376	CDH6 - TCHH	141	213	252	228
PARD3B - TCHH	248	211	244	1	WLS - TCHH	240	105	202	391
PHF24 - TCHH	219	202	239	80	PLAU - TCHH	208	200	234	61
BHLHE41 - TCHH	206	245	176	240	HIVEP3 - TCHH	207	266	175	331
PLCB2 - TCHH	169	287	204	383	FBLN5 - TCHH	298	212	257	88
C1orf162 - TCHH	220	133	249	388	RBMS3 - TCHH	235	255	205	387
LANCL3 - TCHH	222	330	208	213	S100B - TCHH	331	143	375	289
COL26A1 - TCHH	379	24	385	281	SIGLEC16 - TCHH	274	157	347	384
MXRA8 - TCHH	316	95	231	206	VCAM1 - TCHH	281	151	273	319
NLRP3 - TCHH	229	285	247	33	FRZB - TCHH	359	17	350	227
C1QTNF7 - TCHH	334	121	381	265	APBB2 - TCHH	209	203	314	126
HPGD - TCHH	362	100	359	316	F2RL2 - TCHH	347	50	313	357
RHOBTB3 - TCHH	390	118	391	250	EBF1 - TCHH	345	119	354	305
MYOZ3 - TCHH	348	56	356	210	SBSPON - TCHH	337	12	379	358
CA3 - TCHH	357	42	331	226	PDZRN4 - TCHH	383	257	360	268
TMEM130 - TCHH	372	57	351	285	MFAP4 - TCHH	321	96	339	332
NNMT - TCHH	367	16	377	288	PRRT2 - TCHH	313	52	367	353
CYP2S1 - TCHH	307	141	292	377	NT5DC2 - TCHH	214	229	255	382
RAB31 - TCHH	255	90	316	371	ENHO - TCHH	333	201	353	349
CPT1C - TCHH	380	38	277	318	CCDC126 - TCHH	287	391	323	50
STK32A - TCHH	382	33	370	315	GPR27 - TCHH	317	21	270	236
SCG2 - TCHH	355	104	389	219	STARD5 - TCHH	309	289	373	333

Table 1: 2nd order interaction ranking between TCHH VS Individual members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 1 and 2 graphically, with the following influences - • Individual members w.r.t TCHH with TCHH – > APBA2 / COL9A2 / CPA1 / PCOLCE / ENG / CDH6 / PARD3B / WLS / PHF24 / PLAU / BHLHE41 / HIVEP3 / PLCB2 / FBLN5 / C1orf162 / RBMS3 / LANCL3 / S100B / COL26A1 / SIGLEC16 / MXRA8 / VCAM1 / NLRP3 / FRZB / C1QTNF7 / APBB2 / HPGD / F2RL2 / RHOBTB3 / EBF1 / MYOZ3 / SBSPON / CA3 / PDZRN4 / TMEM130 / MFAP4 / NNMT / PRRT2 / CYP2S1 / NT5DC2 / RAB31 / ENHO / CPT1C / CCDC126 / STK32A / GPR27 / SCG2 / STARD5 / HOXB2 / P2RY14 / CABP4 / SLCO3A1 / BOK / MYOZ1 / PDE4DIP / SERTM1 / NME9 / PLAG1 / PLCB1 / NTM / RGS6 / PAPP / OLFML1 / PRKD1 / CSF1 / FLRT2 / PRKG1 / SHC4 / ANKRD20A5P / KBTBD12 / LDLRAD2 / PLAC9 / NUGGC / FAM180A / MME / FAM180B / DLGAP2 / MMP17 / DLL1 / ZNF521 / RYR3 / RHOT1P2 / SYT15 / FAM155A / TMEM240 / VIT / ANKRD20A9P / GPX3 / HMGB3P7 / TENM3 / ITGB2-AS1 / CYP4F29P / SNX18P13.

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS TCHH									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T TCHH									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
HOXB2 - TCHH	325	60	335	339	P2RY14 - TCHH	360	61	301	369
CABP4 - TCHH	273	341	289	93	SLCO3A1 - TCHH	280	11	374	223
BOK - TCHH	221	120	346	203	MYOZ1 - TCHH	335	5	295	341
PDE4DIP - TCHH	319	28	334	386	SERTM1 - TCHH	358	25	392	312
NME9 - TCHH	228	154	274	381	PLAG1 - TCHH	267	322	209	72
PLCB1 - TCHH	328	46	305	270	NTM - TCHH	388	18	376	283
RGS6 - TCHH	369	87	363	320	PAPP - TCHH	392	34	390	200
OLFML1 - TCHH	366	131	336	256	PRKD1 - TCHH	341	117	320	278
CSF1 - TCHH	231	249	341	30	FLRT2 - TCHH	296	64	302	364
PRKG1 - TCHH	320	210	261	340	SHC4 - TCHH	371	72	369	343
ANKRD20A5P - TCHH	378	29	348	300	KBTBD12 - TCHH	303	102	280	354
LDLRAD2 - TCHH	349	98	325	216	PLAC9 - TCHH	368	30	382	258
NUGGC - TCHH	249	78	329	208	FAM180A - TCHH	385	55	352	313
MME - TCHH	342	51	388	292	FAM180B - TCHH	373	36	386	308
DLGAP2 - TCHH	352	169	387	293	MMP17 - TCHH	386	8	357	259
DLL1 - TCHH	343	106	308	301	ZNF521 - TCHH	370	45	333	346
RYR3 - TCHH	292	49	324	334	RHOT1P2 - TCHH	365	76	371	215
SYT15 - TCHH	300	68	236	365	FAM155A - TCHH	376	10	332	337
TMEM240 - TCHH	384	32	269	217	VIT - TCHH	391	71	378	298
ANKRD20A9P - TCHH	374	37	368	286	GPX3 - TCHH	330	65	340	261
HMGB3P7 - TCHH	257	15	361	344	TENM3 - TCHH	387	225	364	237
ITGB2-AS1 - TCHH	381	185	365	348	CYP4F29P - TCHH	363	19	345	272
SNX18P13 - TCHH	350	39	326	326					

Table 2: 2nd order interaction ranking between TCHH VS Individual members.

4. Conclusion

Presented here are a range of multiple synergistic TCHH 2nd order combinations that were ranked via a machine learning based search engine. Via majority voting across the ranking methods, it was possible to find plausible unexplored synergistic combinations of TCHH-X that might be prevalent in meningioma.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Author's contributions

Concept, design, in silico implementation - SS. Analysis and interpretation of results - SS. Manuscript writing - SS. Manuscript revision - SS. Approval of manuscript - SS

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UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

Individual members w.r.t TCHH

APBA2 / COL9A2 / CPA1 / PCOLCE / ENG / CDH6 ...
PARD3B / WLS / PHF24 / PLAU / BHLHE41 / HIVEP3 ...
PLCB2 / FBLN5 / C1orf162 / RBMS3 / LANCL3 ...
S100B / COL26A1 / SIGLEC16 / MXRA8 / VCAM1 ...
NLRP3 / FRZB / C1QTNF7 / APBB2 / HPGD / F2RL2 ...
RHOBTB3 / EBF1 / MYOZ3 / SBSPON / CA3 / PDZRN4 ...
TMEM130 / MFAP4 / NNMT / PRRT2 / CYP2S1 / NT5DC2 ...
RAB31 / ENHO / CPT1C / CCDC126 / STK32A / GPR27 ...
SCG2 / STARD5 / HOXB2 / P2RY14 / CABP4 / SLCO3A1 ...
BOK / MYOZ1 / PDE4DIP / SERTM1 / NME9 / PLAG1 ...
PLCB1 / NTM / RGS6 / PAPP / OLFML1 / PRKD1 ...
CSF1 / FLRT2 / PRKG1 / SHC4 / ANKRD20A5P ...
KBTBD12 / LDLRAD2 / PLAC9 / NUGGC / FAM180A ...
MME / FAM180B / DLGAP2 / MMP17 / DLL1 / ZNF521 ...
RYR3 / RHOT1P2 / SYT15 / FAM155A / TMEM240 / VIT ...
ANKRD20A9P / GPX3 / HMGB3P7 / TENM3 / ITGB2-AS1 ...
CYP4F29P / SNX18P13

TCHH

Table 3: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between TCHH and Individual members.

Source of Data

Data used in this research work was released in a publication in Patel et al. [1]. Permission to use, granted by PNAS.

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